

THE ROLE OF PROVERBS IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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ANNOTATION

Proverbs have been a vivid reflection of people's minds, observations, and attention to the environment, intellect, centuries of life experience, and way of life over the years and centuries. This artistic mirror reflected his attitude to life, nature, man, family and society, his socio-political, spiritual, moral-aesthetic and philosophical views, in short, himself and his identity.

Key words: proverb, national, nation, meaning, definition, word, language, theme.

INTRODUCTION

After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is evidence of how much national spirituality is valued, and the attention to our cultural heritage has changed sharply in a positive direction. That's why everyone should develop the ability to treat folk oral poetry not as an object of recreation, but as a historical document that reflects the national spirit of the people.

Folk art is a labor-intensive kind of public art that is distinct from other forms of folk art "music, theater, dance, game, visual and applied art by its own characteristics." It is also an oral art form that is a component of folk creative activity. It is the craft of language. Oral literature of the Uzbek people includes masterpieces that were created orally by the people themselves, much as there is a rich verbal art that reflects the dream of every nation. Uzbek folk oral poetic creativity is composed of artistic works that have been polished in the performance of their representatives and passed down from generation to generation.

Values of the peoples of the world today connected with its long history roots. First of all, these values are reflected in folklore and the people like other genres of oral creativity, of every nation are a national, literary and cultural treasure. Proverbs are one of the genres of folk art, in which life experiences, aspirations, attitude to the state and society, historical and spiritual state, philosophical, ethnic and aesthetic feelings, and positive qualities of ancestors are embodied.[2] Proverbs have been

refined over the centuries and have become a concise, concise and simple poetic form. Proverbs are usually contextual synonyms.

Every nation has its own folk art, which expresses the value of its nationality. Folk art has preserved its value for centuries. That is, one of the genres of folk art is a proverb. If a person realizes his nationality, he will have his own opinion on proverbs, that is, wise words; it is a wise word passing from mouth to mouth. The proverb is derived from the Arabic word and means “to say”, “to speak”. In proverbs, logic means meaning. Occupies an important place, therefore, they can be used for any purpose of speech. Actually, there are many similarities between Uzbek and English proverbs in Western and Eastern literature. For example, friendship in countries, patriotism, hard work, kindness, justice, and honesty are always praised, but Uzbek proverbs mainly talk about hospitality and honesty, because these values have been considered the face of the Uzbek people since time immemorial. My opinion about the main proverbs is that no matter which country has a proverb, first of all, the values, customs, and nationality of the country should not be lost, only then the country can become a mature and independent exemplary country.

Main part

Proverbs have been living in the speech of different peoples for a long time. Humanity was created to think and draw conclusions about the environment, society, politics, nature, economy and medicine. These thoughts, conclusions, and short and concise sentences form the basis for the creation of proverbs, and these proverbs are accepted not by one person, but by a society and a social group.

If we talk about proverbs in English, first of all, it is no exaggeration to say that the diversity of their composition covers all aspects of the English people. One of the most important of these jewels is proverbs on the theme of the Motherland.

An Englishman's house is his castle. [1]

In fact, no matter how big or small, an Englishman's house is his strong castle. It is described how much the fortress is guarded, even if it costs one's life to preserve its integrity.

Charity begins at home. [1]

Kindness, generosity, and love start from your home. If a person learns these qualities in his family from childhood and matures, then even after he grows up, he will show these good qualities to his friends around him.

Uzbek proverbs laugh at folly and praise wisdom:

Wise men learn by other men's mistakes; fools by themselves.

A wise man draws the necessary conclusions from the foolish behavior of others and tries not to repulse them, only a fool suffers by repeating his mistakes.

No wisdom like silence.

A person does not need much life experience to realize that there is no wisdom beyond silence.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the semantic features of English proverbs differ from those of other nations. Of course, this nation's geographical location, international politics, religion, culture, traditions, social origin and lifestyle had a great impact on this. Proverbs are usually contextual synonyms. Among the synonyms of proverbs, a proverb characterized by dominance is clearly visible. It is necessary to distinguish variant, doublet and synonymy in proverbs. As in the synonymous line, in the synonymous line of proverbs, proverbs with an old/new color are distinguished.[3] Among the proverbs in the folk language, some of them are widely used in speech, while others may be shortened, and in addition, they may completely disappear and give way to new ones.

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